

Processing and High Temperature Oxidation Behavior of Polymer Derived Ceramic Coatings with Passive Fillers

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ABSTRACT

The work is aimed at the development of an oxidation resistant environmental barrier coating system on steel substrates. The preparation of the coatings consists of the two main steps: the synthesis of the powder filler AYZ ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) via Pechini sol-gel route and the processing of the coatings. The composition of the AYZ filler is derived from $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ eutectic (76,8 mol. % Al_2O_3 , 23,2 mol. % Y_2O_3) and modified by the addition of 20 mol. % ZrO_2 . The PDC system consists of two layers that were consecutively applied to stainless steel (AISI 441) substrates. The bond-coat was prepared from pre-ceramic polymer PHPS (perhydropolysilazane) by dip-coating of the ultrasonically cleaned metal sheets. The pyrolysis of the bond-coat was performed in air at the temperature of 500 °C for 1 h. The top-coat was prepared from the ceramic matrix forming polysilazane HTT 1800 precursor (19 vol. %), filled with yttria-stabilized zirconia (30 vol. %) and AYZ powder as passive filler (21 vol. %), and the commercial barium silicate glass particles (30 vol. %, Schott AG) as sealing agents. The resulting mixture was applied onto bond-coat by spray coating technique and the curing of the composite coatings was performed in air at the temperature of 800 °C with a holding time of 1 h. High temperature oxidation tests were carried out in a high temperature horizontal electric tube furnace (Clasic 0213T, Clasic, Praha, Czech Republic) at the temperatures of 900 °C, 950 °C and 1000 °C and the exposure times in the range of 1 – 48 hours in flowing atmosphere of synthetic air (purity 99.5%, Linde, Slovakia).

Fig. 1 presents the morphology of the AYZ powder reconstituted through freeze drying technique. SEM examination revealed the irregular and angular shape of the grains as a result of crushing process of the synthesised powder. The diffraction pattern of the AYZ powder is shown in Fig 2. XRD pattern revealed the presence of tetragonal zirconium oxide and yttrium-aluminium garnet (YAG) phases, along with the trace of yttrium-aluminium oxide (YAIO_3).

Fig. 3: SEM micrograph of the AYZ powder

Fig. 4: X-Ray diffraction pattern of the AYZ powder

In a Fig. 3, a SEM micrograph of a HTT 1800/glass composite coating after pyrolysis in air is presented. After thermal treatment in air at 800 °C, uniform, well adherent and crack-free composite coating on stainless steel were prepared. It can be concluded that the addition of powder filler AYZ was effective at preventing the formation of cracks and pores. The addition of the filler enables the

formation of a rigid skeletal structure in the coating thus facilitating escape of gases during the pyrolytic conversion of the organosilicon precursor. XRD pattern of the coating is displayed in the Fig. 4. After pyrolysis in air the polysilazane-based coating contains three crystalline phases, namely monoclinic and tetragonal ZrO_2 , and YAG, originating from the powder filler AYZ.

Fig. 3: Cross-sectional SEM image of the coating after pyrolysis in air at 800 °C

Fig. 4: X-Ray diffraction pattern of the coating after pyrolysis in air at 800°C

From the weight gain measurements after oxidation tests (Fig. 5) it is obvious that the tested layers provide effective protection from oxidation of stainless steel at 900 °C and 950 °C. Compared to uncoated samples, only negligible mass loss was observed at the oxidation temperature of 900°C and 950°C. No significant corrosion damage was observed by SEM analysis (Fig. 6), coating appeared to be well adherent at these temperatures. Moreover, the cracks present on the surface of as-prepared coatings gradually healed due to the softening of the used glass additives. However, at the temperature of 1000 °C and after 24 hours of oxidation, a significant weight loss was observed due to the progressive cracking and peeling off the protective layer.

Fig. 5: Weight changes after oxidation tests at various temperatures and holding times

Fig. 6: SEM cross-sections of the coating after oxidation tests at 900°C/48h

Keywords: high-temperature oxidation, passive filler, polymer-derived ceramics

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